

Sparsity-Aware Tensor Decomposition

Abstract—Sparse tensor decomposition, such as Canonical Polyadic Decomposition (CPD), is a key operation for data analytics and machine learning. Its computation is dominated by a set of MTTKRP (Matricized Tensor Times Khatri Rao Product) operations. The collection of required MTTKRP operations for sparse CPD include common sub-computations across them and many approaches exist to factorize and reuse common sub-expressions. Prior work on sparse CPD has focused on minimizing the number of high-level operators. In this paper, we consider a design space that covers whether the partial MTTKRP results should be saved, different mode permutations and model the total volume of data movement to/from memory. Also, we propose a fine-grained load balancing method that supports higher levels of parallelization.

Index Terms—CPD, MTTKRP, sparse tensor factorization

I. INTRODUCTION

Sparse tensor decomposition, such as Canonical Polyadic Decomposition (CPD), is a key operation for data analytics and machine learning. The computation is dominated by a set of MTTKRP (Matricized Tensor Times Khatri Rao Product) operations [1]. Several research efforts have addressed the development of efficient parallel implementations of sparse MTTKRP [2]–[6]

Consider the CP decomposition of a 4D tensor $\mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l)$ into a product of four 2D matrices $A(i, r)$, $B(j, r)$, $C(k, r)$, and $D(l, r)$:

$$T(i, j, k, l) \approx \sum_r A(i, r)B(j, r)C(k, r)D(l, r)$$

The MTTKRP operation thus computes:

$$\tilde{A}(i, r) = \sum_{j, k, l} \mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l)B(j, r)C(k, r)D(l, r)$$

The iterative algorithm for CPD of an N-dimensional tensor involves a sequence of N MTTKRP operations. For example, CPD of a 4D tensor requires a sequence of 4 MTTKRP operations in a loop until convergence is achieved:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{A}(i, r) &= \sum_{j, k, l} \mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l)B(j, r)C(k, r)D(l, r); A_n = f(\tilde{A}) \\ \tilde{B}(j, r) &= \sum_{i, k, l} \mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l)A_n(i, r)C(k, r)D(l, r); B_n = f(\tilde{B}) \\ \tilde{C}(k, r) &= \sum_{i, j, l} \mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l)A_n(i, r)B_n(j, r)D(l, r); C_n = f(\tilde{C}) \\ \tilde{D}(l, r) &= \sum_{i, j, k} \mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l)A_n(i, r)B_n(j, r)C_n(k, r); D_n = f(\tilde{D}) \\ A &= A_n; B = B_n; C = C_n; D = D_n \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

It may be seen in this example that the set of 4 MTTKRP operations involves some common sub-expressions and therefore computations can be saved by computing, storing and

reusing intermediate tensors corresponding to some common sub-expressions in the collection of MTTKRP computations. For example, the first two MTTKRP operations in the above sequence of 4 MTTKRP operations can be performed using fewer arithmetic operations if the intermediate tensor \mathcal{I} is computed and stored as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}(i, j, r) &= \sum_{k, l} \mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l)C(k, r)D(l, r); \\ \tilde{A}(i, r) &= \sum_j \mathcal{I}(i, j, r)B(j, r); A_n = f(\tilde{A}) \\ \tilde{B}(j, r) &= \sum_i \mathcal{I}(i, j, r)A_n(i, r); B_n = f(\tilde{B}) \end{aligned}$$

This idea of restructuring the computation, storing and reusing an intermediate result is termed as *memoization*. It has been well studied in previous works [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12]. A key question in this context is that of determining which of many alternative memoization schemes is the best. Dense tensor factorization has more regular computations, therefore a comparative analysis is easier in that context [13]. The design and implementation of an efficient memoization scheme for sparse tensors is more challenging because of the constraints on efficient data access imposed by any compact representation of sparse tensors (such as the CSF) and the resultant irregularity of the data access patterns.

In comparison with prior studies on efficient sparse MTTKRP for tensor factorization, we make the following contributions in this paper:

- We consider a more extensive design space of memoization schemes, and implement a collection of parallel kernels for each scheme. In comparison to prior works that store several reordered copies of the tensor, we keep a single representation of the input tensor, in the standard memory-efficient CSF format.
- We develop a sparsity-aware model of data movement. Such a model allows rapid search of the design space of memoized configurations. Fast dynamic selection of this configuration for a given sparse tensor is then used to accelerate the decomposition.
- We develop a novel scheme for load-balanced parallel execution of the selected memoization scheme on shared-memory multiprocessors.
- We combine all our optimizations in a STeF (Sparse Tensor Factorization) implementation and we demonstrate the superior performance over several prior schemes with publicly available codebases, including AdaTM [4], ALTO [5], SPLATT [2], [14] and TACO [15].

II. BACKGROUND

A. Mathematical preliminaries

Tensors can be used to store multidimensional data from several domains. In order to compress this information, the tensor can be decomposed into a set of matrices. Such a decomposition leverages several binary operators that work with combinations of tensors, matrices and vectors. Kolda et al. [1] provides a comprehensive overview of all such operators. We now define the ones used specifically in the context of CP decomposition, ie the scope of this work.

Khatri-Rao product (KRP): For matrices $A \in \mathbb{R}^{I \times R}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{J \times R}$, the Khatri-Rao product (KRP) is a matrix $M \in \mathbb{R}^{(IJ) \times R}$ and often represented with \odot sign. As can be inferred from the shapes, this operator performs an element-wise product of each row of A with each row of B . There is no reduction operation in the sequence.

Tensor Times Matrix (TTM) product: This product unfolds of the tensor $\mathcal{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{I_0 \times \dots \times I_{d-1}}$ along dimension i into a matrix $T \in \mathbb{R}^{I_i \times (A_0 \dots A_{i-1} A_{i+1} \dots A_{d-1})}$ then performs GEMM with another with a matrix $M \in \mathbb{R}^{I_i \times R}$.

Tensor Times Vector (TTV) product: For given tensor $T \in \mathbb{R}^{I_1 \times \dots \times I_k \times \dots \times I_n}$, the product with vector $V \in \mathbb{R}^{I_k}$ yields another tensor of shape $I_1 \times \dots \times I_n$, without the k^{th} dimension. A naive implementation would perform an elementwise product of each fibre of T (in the k^{th} dimension) with the vector V , and add them all up.

B. The Compressed Sparse Fiber (CSF) format for storing tensors

In order to save memory, sparse tensors are not stored as N dimensional arrays. Instead, they are stored as trees in a format called Compressed Sparse Fibre (CSF) [2]. For an N dimensional tensor, the corresponding tree will have $N - 1$ depth. Each level represents one dimension of the tensor. The leaf level, however, stores the non-zero values from the tensor. Each internal node stores the indices of the non-zero fibres of the tensor in the dimension corresponding to the depth of the node.

Therefore, the total number of nodes of the tree (ie. the memory needed to store the sparse tensor) depends on the order of dimensions in the tree. This is also called the "mode-order" of the CSF structure. A common heuristic is to sort the dimensions in increasing order of length, assign them from root to leaf in this order.

Alg. 1 shows simple (unoptimized) pseudocode for a 4D MTTKRP operation of 4D tensor \mathcal{T} using CSF structure.

III. OVERVIEW

In this section, we provide a high-level overview of the key ideas incorporated in the new memoized MTTKRP approach for CPD presented in this paper. We begin by presenting notations used in describing the sequence of operations invoked for the memoized execution.

Algorithm 1: Simple pseudo-code for MTTKRP using a 4D tensor \mathcal{T} using CSF pointers.

```

//  $\tilde{A} = \text{MTTKRP}(\mathcal{T}, B, C, D)$ 
input : Sparse tensor  $\mathcal{T}$  is a 4D tensor.  $B$ ,  $C$  and  $D$ 
        represent the factorization matrices.  $R$  is the rank of
        decomposition.
output: Output  $\tilde{A}$  needed to update factorization matrix  $A$ 
1  $num\_slice \leftarrow$  Number of slices in the tensor
2 for  $i_p = 0$  to  $num\_slice-1$  do in parallel
3    $i \leftarrow \text{indexI}[i_p]$ 
4   for  $j_p = \text{ptrI}[i_p]$  to  $\text{ptrI}[i_p+1]-1$  do
5      $j \leftarrow \text{indexJ}[j_p]$ 
6     for  $k_p = \text{ptrJ}[j_p]$  to  $\text{ptrJ}[j_p+1]-1$  do
7        $k \leftarrow \text{indexK}[k_p]$ 
8       for  $l_p = \text{ptrK}[k_p]$  to  $\text{ptrK}[k_p+1]-1$  do
9          $l \leftarrow \text{indexL}[l_p]$ 
10        for  $r$  in  $[0:R-1]$  do
11           $\tilde{A}(i,r) \leftarrow \tilde{A}(i,r) + \mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l) * B(j,r)$ 
             $* C(k,r) * D(l,r)$ 

```

A. Notations

We use \mathcal{T} to denote a tensor. Let d be the dimensionality of the tensor and $M^{(0)}, M^{(1)}, \dots, M^{(d-1)}$ be the factor matrices each of rank R .

Subscript ($_X$): The ($_X$) subscript that follows a tensor name denote that the data type is a vector of size X . ($_1$) means scalar data type and ($_R$) means data type is a vector of size R .

$M_{-1}^{(i)}$ and $v_{-R}^{(i)}$: The matrix $M_{-1}^{(i)}$ is the factor matrix for mode i . The number of columns for every factor matrix is the number of ranks, R . We can view $M_{-1}^{(i)}$ as a 2D matrix whose elements are scalars or as a vector of elements whose data type is a vector of size R . Thus, in this paper we use $v_{-R}^{(i)}$ as an alias for $M_{-1}^{(i)}$.

$K_{-R}^{(i)}$: This notation denotes KRP product of factor matrices $M_{-1}^{(0)}, M_{-1}^{(1)}, \dots, M_{-1}^{(i)}$ for $i > 0$. $K_{-R}^{(i)}$ can be represented using the recurrence relation $K_{-R}^{(i)} = K_{-R}^{(i-1)} \odot v_{-R}^{(i)}$, $K_{-R}^{(0)} = v_{-R}^{(0)} = M_{-1}^{(0)}$ as the base case.

$T_{-R}^{(i)}$: Represents the partial MTTKRP result after KRP of $M_{-1}^{(i+1)}, M_{-1}^{(i+2)}, \dots, M_{-1}^{(d-1)}$ are contracted from the \mathcal{T} . Therefore, using a TTM operation we get $T_{-R}^{(d-2)} = \mathcal{T} * M_{-1}^{(d-1)}$ is a $d-1$ dimensional tensor with data type of a vector of size R . Similarly, using TTV operation for $i < d-2$ we get $T_{-R}^{(i)} = T_{-R}^{(i+1)} * v_{-R}^{(i+1)}$.

MTTV: Similar to MTTKRP, we define MTTV as the Matricized Tensor Times Vector operation.

B. The space of memoized schemes

Algorithm 2 shows the CPD-ALS algorithm for a 4D tensor. In our notation, we will refer to A , B , C and D in this algorithm as $M_{-1}^{(0)}$, $M_{-1}^{(1)}$, $M_{-1}^{(2)}$ and $M_{-1}^{(3)}$. Fig. 1 illustrates different options for updating $M_{-1}^{(1)}$. The factor matrices $M_{-1}^{(0)}$, $M_{-1}^{(1)}$, $M_{-1}^{(2)}$, and $M_{-1}^{(3)}$ correspond to the modes 0, 1, 2, 3, respectively. Fig. 1(a) shows a sequence of three tensor operations to produce $M_{-1}^{(0)}$: i) A TTM

Algorithm 2: CPD-ALS code for a 4D tensor

input : \mathcal{T} a 4D tensor, with size $I \times J \times K \times L$
output: Factorization matrices A, B, C and D with sizes $I \times R, J \times R, K \times R$ and $L \times R$ respectively and λ

```

1 for  $it = 1$  to  $max\ iterations$  do
2    $A \leftarrow \mathcal{T}_{(0)}(B \odot C \odot D)(B^T B C^T C D^T D)^{-1}$ 
3   Normalize columns of  $A$  and save norms in  $\lambda$ 
4    $B \leftarrow \mathcal{T}_{(1)}(A \odot C \odot D)(A^T A C^T C D^T D)^{-1}$ 
5   Normalize columns of  $B$  and save norms in  $\lambda$ 
6    $C \leftarrow \mathcal{T}_{(2)}(A \odot B \odot D)(A^T A B^T B D^T D)^{-1}$ 
7   Normalize columns of  $C$  and save norms in  $\lambda$ 
8    $D \leftarrow \mathcal{T}_{(3)}(A \odot B \odot C)(A^T A B^T B C^T C)^{-1}$ 
9   Normalize columns of  $D$  and save norms in  $\lambda$ 
10  if Convergence condition met then
11    exit loop

```

Fig. 1: Computation of the factor matrix corresponding to mode 1 that is not the root of the CSF tree. This is done after contracting out mode 0. Depending on what was saved, mode 1 computation can be done in 3 ways as per b), c), or d).

(Tensor Times Matrix) operation $\mathcal{T}(i, j, k, l) * M_{-1}^{(3)}(l, r)$ to produce $T_{-R}^{(2)}(i, j, k)$; ii) A TTV (Tensor Times Vector) operation $T_{-R}^{(2)}(i, j, k) * M_{-1}^{(2)}(k, r)$ to produce $T_{-R}^{(1)}(i, j)$; iii) A TTV operation $T_{-R}^{(1)}(i, j, r) * M_{-1}^{(1)}(j, r)$ to produce $M_{-1}^{(0)}(i, r)$. Fig. 1(b-d) show three options for producing $M_{-1}^{(1)}$. Fig. 1(b) shows how it can be produced with a minimal number of additional arithmetic operations, using saved intermediate tensor $T_{-R}^{(1)}(i, j)$ by performing the MTTV operation $M_{-1}^{(0)}(i, r) * T_{-R}^{(1)}(i, j)$ to produce $M_{-1}^{(1)}(j, r)$.

Another option is to use the saved intermediate tensor $T_{-R}^{(2)}(i, j, k)$, by repeating the TTV operation $T_{-R}^{(2)}(i, j, k) * M_{-1}^{(2)}(k, r)$ and fuse that computation with a MTTV operation with $M_{-1}^{(0)}(i, r)$, as shown in Fig. 1(c). Finally, it is also possible to produce $M_{-1}^{(1)}(j, r)$ without reusing any of the computation used in producing $M_{-1}^{(0)}$, as shown in Fig. 1(d).

Note that these choices represent different amounts of

computation and data movement. While memoization can save arithmetic operations, it introduces additional data movement, which could offset the benefits of memoization, especially since data movement is much more expensive than arithmetic operations. In Sec. V we develop an analytical model to evaluate the efficacy of alternate memoization schemes.

C. Load-balanced work distribution

Prior works [2], [4] rely on the CSF format to divide slices at the root mode and assign each chunk to a thread (Figure 2a). Such an approach can result in load imbalance if the number of slices at the root mode is less than the number of threads and/or the non-zeros are non-uniformly distributed across the slices. For example, in the tensors *vast-2015-mc1-3d* and *vast-2015-mc1-5d*, the number of slices at the root mode (for mode-length ordered CSF representation) is just 2. Therefore, this work division scheme can only utilize 2 threads. Furthermore, a 2-way partitioning for these tensors will also result in 1674% load imbalance, as a virtue of the distribution of non-zeros.

We propose a fine-grained work division strategy where all threads process roughly the same number of non-zeros. Simply dividing the non-zeros across threads may result in write conflict. For example, consider Figure 2b, where both threads 1 and 2 write to the same location at level 0 (similar conflict also occurs at level 1). To ensure correctness we could use atomic updates; however, the cost of atomic operations will degrade the performance. Another option is to use privatization, **keeping a private copy for each thread**, but it increases the amount of data movement.

We devise a scheme that efficiently avoids the write conflict without using atomic operations or privatization. Our approach is based on the observation that the write conflicts, if any, will only occur at the boundary elements between the threads. The maximum number of elements that will potentially have write conflict is \mathcal{T} , where \mathcal{T} is the number of threads. The write conflicts can be avoided by replicating just the boundary elements, i.e., instead of writing to a tensor of size $N * R$, where N is the number of rows and R is the number of features, we write to a tensor of size $(N + \mathcal{T}) * R$. After generating this matrix, the replicated elements are reduced to form the final result. The cost of this reduction is considerably less than the cost of using atomic updates or privatization. The details of this scheme is presented in Section IV-A.

D. Switching Mode Order of Last Two Modes

Consider the sequence of steps for computing MTTKRP for a single-mode, e.g., for mode-0 in Fig. 1. It requires one TTM operation using all non-zeros of the tensor T , followed by a series of TTV operations using successively lower dimensional tensors that result from the TTM/TTV operations. At each stage, the number of non-zeros in the output tensor is lower than the input tensor by a factor corresponding to the average number of non-zeros per fiber along the contracted dimension of the input tensor. If the non-zeros in the input tensor T were uniformly distributed over the index space, the average number of non-zeros per fiber would be proportional to the

Fig. 2: Work distribution for 5 threads. Fig. 2a shows work distribution with outer-mode slice based granularity. Since there are only 4 slices at the root mode, no more than 4 threads get any work. The maximum number of nodes traversed by a thread is 12 (yellow thread) while thread 4 (blue) has no work. Fig. 2b shows the STeF work distribution. Squares with two colors are traversed by 2 threads. The maximum number of nodes traversed by a thread is 9 (orange thread) and the lightest load is 6 nodes (blue thread).

Fig. 3: STeF load balance for 5 threads. Squares with two colors are traversed by 2 threads. The maximum number of nodes traversed by a thread is 9 (orange thread) and the lightest load is 6 nodes (blue thread).

mode lengths. If so, it would be best to order the modes in the CSF representation in increasing order of mode lengths so that a maximal compression is achieved in the number of non-zeros of the series of lower-dimensional tensors, thereby minimizing the total work in terms of the number of operations.

However, the average fiber length along different dimensions of a tensor is not always directly related to the mode lengths. For example, in delicious-4d, the average fiber length for the the longest mode of length 17 million is 1.5 whereas the same stat for the mode of length 2 million is 3. If the average fiber length is not longest along the longest mode, it would be preferable to use one of the other modes as the “fiber” mode in the CSF representation. While it would be very expensive to determine the average fiber length corresponding to all modes of a tensor, we have devised a very efficient algorithm to determine the average fiber length for the last two modes. We therefore consider swapping of the last two modes in the CSF representation. It also turns out that in practice, the longest average fiber length turns out to almost always to be one among the two longest tensor modes.

IV. ALGORITHMS & OPTIMIZATIONS

A. Load-balanced work distribution

Algorithm 3: Finding thread start position of CSF representation of \mathcal{T}

input : d dimensional sparse tensor \mathcal{T}
output: 2D thread_start array showing thread starting position for each level of the CSF for each thread

```

1 for th=0 to number of threads do in parallel
2   thread_start[th][d-1] ← th * nnz / number of threads
3 for th=0 to number of threads do in parallel
4   for i = d - 2 to 0 do
5     thread_start[th][i] ←
       fin_parent_CSF(thread_start[th][i+1])

```

As mentioned earlier, load balance plays an important role in determining performance. As shown in Figure 2, compared to the default scheme (Figure 2a), where the last thread was idle, our scheme eliminates thread idling and achieves a good load balance. The key to achieving high performance is to deliver good load balance without suffering from the overhead of atomics operations and additional data movement from privatization. First, we divide the non-zeros equally among each thread. Algorithm 3 shows how the start locations for each thread are computed. Each thread is first assigned an equal number of non-zeros, and the start position of each thread is found by looking at the parent of non-zeros at the boundaries (fin_parent_CSF). Since we distribute nnzs across the threads, multiple threads may write to the same memory location in the upper levels of the tree and thus might cause write conflicts. Figure 3 shows our data structure. The original scheme uses an array of size N_0 , whereas our scheme uses an array of size $N_0 + T$, where N_0 is the length of mode 0, and T is the number of threads. Only the elements at the thread boundary can have write conflicts; hence our scheme replicates these elements. For example, in Figure 3, the locations corresponding to slice 0, 2, and 3 is replicated as these are the boundary elements. Index 0 of the array is

assigned to thread 0, index 1-3 is assigned to thread 1, index 4 is assigned to thread 2, index 5-6 is assigned to thread 3, and index 7 is assigned to thread 7. The entire array is initialized to zero, and each thread processes the elements assigned to it and makes the corresponding contributions to its designated memory locations.

Algorithm 4: Reducing the factorization matrix of the root mode of the CSF representation

input : Factorization matrix F which is the root mode in CSF
output: Reduced Factorization matrix F

```

1 for  $th = 1$  to number of threads - 1 do
2   boundary  $\leftarrow$  thread_start[th][0]
3   //combine contributions at boundaries
4    $F[\text{boundary}][:] \leftarrow F[\text{boundary}][:] + F[\text{boundary}+th][:]$ 
5    $F[\text{boundary}+th][:] \leftarrow 0$ 
6   start  $\leftarrow$  thread_start[th][0] + 1
7   end  $\leftarrow$  thread_start[th+1][0]
8   //move elements to the left
9   for  $el = \text{start}$  to end do
10     $F[el][:] \leftarrow F[el+th][:]$ 
11     $F[el][:] \leftarrow 0$ 

```

The next step is to combine the contributions from multiple threads. For example, both thread 1 and thread 2 makes contribution to slice 2. Algorithm 4 shows how this combination is done. *thread_start* array in line 2 shows the starting position for each thread at each level and it is pointing to indices in CSF structure. In Line 4, we add the contributions from the boundary elements and the loop in Line 9, shifts the elements towards left such that the replicated space can be removed. Thus padded array of size $N_0 + T$ is shrunk back to an array of size T_0 . For example, consider slice 2 in fig. 3 which is split across thread 1 and thread 2. We first combine the values at index 4 and index 5 which corresponds to the contribution from thread 1 and thread 2 towards slice 2. We then shift the remaining elements towards the left.

B. Sparsity Aware MTTKRP

Algorithm 5: MTTKRP for mode u in tensor \mathcal{T}

input : Tensor \mathcal{T} in CSF format and factorization matrices $\mathcal{A} = \{A_0, A_1, \dots, A_{d-1}\}$, MTTKRP mode u
output: Updated factorization matrix \hat{A}_u

```

1 for  $th=0$  to number of threads - 1 do in parallel
2   for  $i=\text{thread\_start}[th][0]$  to  $\text{thread\_start}[th+1][0]$  do
3     if  $u \neq 0$  then
4        $k_0(:) \leftarrow M_{-1}^{(0)}$ 
5       MTTKRP-LOOP( $u, th, 1, i$ )
6     if  $u = 0$  then
7        $M_{-1}^{(0)}[i+th, :] \leftarrow t_0$ 
8   if  $u=0$  then
9     Call the code for reducing root mode (Algorithm 4)
10  else if  $Is M_{-1}^{(u)}$  privatized? then
11    Reduce  $M_{-1}^{(u)}$ 

```

Algorithm 6: MTTKRP-LOOP

input : MTTKRP mode u , thread id th , loop id i , pindex

```

1 start  $\leftarrow$  MAX(thread_start[th][i],  $\mathcal{T}.\text{ptr}[i-1][\text{pindex}]$ )
2 end  $\leftarrow$  MIN(thread_start[th+1][i],  $\mathcal{T}.\text{ptr}[i-1][\text{pindex}+1]$ )
3 for  $idx = \text{start}$  to end do
4   if  $\mathcal{T}.\text{save}[i]$  and ( $u = 0$  or  $i \geq u$ ) then
5      $t_i(:) \leftarrow T_{-R}^{(i)}[\mathcal{T}.\text{ptr}[i]+th]$ 
6   if  $i < u$  then
7      $k_i(:) \leftarrow k_{i-1}(:) \odot M_{-1}^{(i)}[idx, :]$ 
8   if  $\neg \mathcal{T}.\text{save}[i]$  or  $u > i$  or  $u = 0$  then
9     if  $i < d - 1$  then
10      MTTKRP-LOOP( $u, th, i+1, idx$ )
11    else
12       $Tval \leftarrow \mathcal{T}.\text{val}[idx]$ 
13      if  $u = d - 1$  then
14         $M_{-1}^{(d-1)}[idx, :] \leftarrow M_{-1}^{(d-1)}[idx, :] +$ 
15           $Tval * k_{i-1}(:)$ 
16      else
17         $t_{i-1}(:) \leftarrow t_{i-1}(:) + Tval * M_{-1}^{(d-1)}[idx, :]$ 
18  if  $i = u$  then
19     $M_{-1}^{(i)}[idx, :] \leftarrow \overline{M_{-1}^{(i)}}[idx, :] + k_{i-1}(:) \odot t_i(:)$ 
20  else if  $i > u$  then
21     $t_i(:) \leftarrow t_{i+1}(:) \odot M_{-1}^{(i)}[idx, :]$ 

```

This section explains how all the optimizations proposed in this paper are put together to generate the complete MTTKRP code. MTTKRP for the first mode of the CSF is implemented as a series of dot products, whereas MTTKRP for the last mode of the CSF is a series of Khatri-Rao products. MTTKRP for the internal modes can therefore be written as a combination of dot products and KRPs. Algorithm 5 shows the generic MTTKRP algorithm for any mode, where Algorithm 6 shows the generic loop structure.

Algorithms 5 and 6 compute the MTTKRP of mode u by using $\overline{M_{-1}^{(u)}} = K_{-R}^{(u-1)} * T_{-R}^{(u)}$, for $0 < u < d - 1$. For $u = 0$, $\overline{M_{-1}^{(0)}} = T_{-R}^{(0)}$ and for $u = d - 1$, $\overline{M_{-1}^{(d-1)}} = \mathcal{T}_{(d-1)} * K_{-R}^{(d-2)}$, which is the original MTTKRP formulation. Vectors t_i and k_i hold a row of $T_{-R}^{(i)}$ and $K_{-R}^{(i)}$ respectively. In order to prevent race condition in the thread_start boundaries for updating $\overline{M_{-1}^{(0)}}$, each thread writes into location $i + th$ instead of i in line 7 and line 9 of the Algorithm 5 calls algorithm 4 to shrink $\overline{M_{-1}^{(0)}}$ to its original size. If $u > 0$, then for updating $\overline{M_{-1}^{(u)}}$ either atomic updates are needed or each thread needs to hold its own copy meaning it needs to be privatized. If $\overline{M_{-1}^{(u)}}$ is privatized line 11 of Algorithm 5 is executed to reduce it to a single matrix.

In Algorithm 6, k_i vector holds a row of KRP of the matrices $\overline{M_{-1}^{(0)}}, \dots, \overline{M_{-1}^{(i)}}$. Similarly, t_i holds a row of partial MTTKRP result after contracting out $\overline{M_{-1}^{(i+1)}}, \dots, \overline{M_{-1}^{(d-1)}}$. Thus, in order to compute the values $\overline{M_{-1}^{(u)}}[i_u, :]$, we need to do a Hadamard product of k_{u-1} and t_u . $\mathcal{T}.\text{save}$ is an array of boolean values where $\mathcal{T}.\text{save}[i]$ denotes whether the partial MTTKRP result $T_{-R}^{(i)}$ after contracting out matrices $\overline{M_{-1}^{(i+1)}}, \dots, \overline{M_{-1}^{(d-1)}}$ is to be stored or not. $\mathcal{T}.\text{ptr}[i][idx]$ is a pointer array pointing the start

position of children of node idx in mode i to mode $i+1$. $\mathcal{T}.val$ is the array holding values of the tensor.

As per the work distribution in Algorithm 3, two threads might want to access the same location for a write operation. In the implementation, each thread uses a localised copy of $T_{-R}^{(i)}$ array by shifting its write location by an amount equal to its thread id. More specifically, if thread th and $th+1$ want to write to the same data location s , one of them writes $s+th$ and the other writes $s+(th+1)$, hence avoiding a race condition.

Algorithm 7 implements Figure 1b where partial MTTKRP for $T_{-R}^{(1)}(i,j)$ is stored. Using the partial results, we can compute MTTKRP for $M_{-1}^{(1)}$ using a single MTTV operation. Algorithm 8 describes the case in Figure 1c where $M_{-1}^{(2)}$ needs to be contracted out. First, $M_{-1}^{(2)}$ is contracted out from $T_{-R}^{(2)}(i,j,k)$, the partial MTTKRP and the MTTV operation is performed to get updated values of B. Finally, Algorithm 9 implements Figure 1d in which there aren't any saved results; thus, the entire CSF structure is traversed to compute the MTTKRP for $M_{-1}^{(1)}$.

Algorithm 7: STeF MTTKRP to compute $M_{-1}^{(1)}$ for a 4D tensor \mathcal{T} where $T_{-R}^{(1)}$ is stored.

input : Sparse tensor \mathcal{T} , factorization matrices $M_{-1}^{(0)}, M_{-1}^{(1)}, M_{-1}^{(2)}$ and $M_{-1}^{(3)}$, number of factors R
output: Updated factorization matrix \hat{B}

```

1 for  $i \in \mathcal{T}(*,*,*,:)$  do in parallel
2    $k_0 \leftarrow M_{-1}^{(0)}[i,:]$ 
3   for  $j \in \mathcal{T}(i,*,*,:)$  do
4      $t_1 \leftarrow T_{-R}^{(1)}[i,j]$ 
5      $M_{-1}^{(1)}(j,:) \leftarrow M_{-1}^{(1)}(j,:) + t_1(\cdot) \odot k_0(\cdot)$ 
6 if  $M_{-1}^{(1)}$  is privatized then
7   Reduce  $M_{-1}^{(1)}$ 

```

Algorithm 8: STeF MTTKRP to compute $M_{-1}^{(1)}$ for a 4D tensor \mathcal{T} where $T_{-R}^{(2)}$ is stored.

input : Sparse tensor \mathcal{T} , factorization matrices $M_{-1}^{(0)}, M_{-1}^{(1)}, M_{-1}^{(2)}$ and $M_{-1}^{(3)}$, number of factors R
output: Updated factorization matrix \hat{B}

```

1 for  $i \in \mathcal{T}(*,*,*,:)$  do in parallel
2    $k_0 \leftarrow M_{-1}^{(0)}[i,:]$ 
3   for  $j \in \mathcal{T}(i,*,*,:)$  do
4      $t_1 \leftarrow$  zero vector of length  $R$ 
5     for  $k \in \mathcal{T}(i,j,*,:)$  do
6        $t_2 \leftarrow T_{-R}^{(2)}[i,j,k]$ 
7        $t_1(\cdot) \leftarrow t_1(\cdot) + t_2(\cdot) \odot M_{-1}^{(2)}(k,:)$ 
8      $M_{-1}^{(1)}(j,:) \leftarrow M_{-1}^{(1)}(j,:) + t_1(\cdot) \odot k_0(\cdot)$ 
9 if  $M_{-1}^{(1)}$  is privatized then
10  Reduce  $M_{-1}^{(1)}$ 

```

V. MODELS

This section motivates the need to model the impact of memoization and mode order switching on data movement.

Algorithm 9: STeF MTTKRP to compute $M_{-1}^{(1)}$ for 4D tensor \mathcal{T} where no partial results are stored.

input : Sparse tensor \mathcal{T} , factorization matrices $M_{-1}^{(0)}, M_{-1}^{(1)}, M_{-1}^{(2)}$ and $M_{-1}^{(3)}$, number of factors R
output: Updated factorization matrix \hat{B}

```

1 for  $i \in \mathcal{T}(*,*,*,:)$  do in parallel
2    $k_0 \leftarrow M_{-1}^{(0)}[i,:]$ 
3   for  $j \in \mathcal{T}(i,*,*,:)$  do
4      $t_1 \leftarrow$  zero vector of length  $R$ 
5     for  $k \in \mathcal{T}(i,j,*,:)$  do
6        $t_2 \leftarrow$  zero vector of length  $R$ 
7       for  $l \in \mathcal{T}(i,j,k,*)$  do
8          $Tval \leftarrow \mathcal{T}(i,j,k,l)$ 
9          $t_2(\cdot) \leftarrow t_2(\cdot) + Tval * M_{-1}^{(3)}(l,:)$ 
10       $t_1(\cdot) \leftarrow t_1(\cdot) + t_2(\cdot) \odot M_{-1}^{(2)}(k,:)$ 
11       $M_{-1}^{(1)}(j,:) \leftarrow M_{-1}^{(1)}(j,:) + t_1(\cdot) \odot k_0(\cdot)$ 
12 if  $M_{-1}^{(1)}$  is privatized then
13  Reduce  $M_{-1}^{(1)}$ 

```

We also develop an analytical model to quantify the expected data movement and, thereby, the performance.

A. Saving Partial Results

As shown in Section I, a single CPD iteration involves multiple MTTKRPs, some of which share the same intermediate results. Rather than recomputing the intermediate results for each MTTKRP, they could be computed once and reused thereafter; this strategy is called memoization. While memoization helps to reduce the total number of computations, it introduces additional memory write and read operations to save and load the intermediate results. Depending on the operand sizes, this additional data movement can overwhelm the savings from the reduced number of operations. Consider for example, the *uber* tensor described in Table I. Saving all the intermediate results for the decomposition of this tensor requires 62M reads and 22M writes. However, not saving the biggest partial result will result in 24M reads and 238K writes, which makes the decomposition faster.

In contrast for vast-2015-mc1-3d tensor, saving the intermediate tensor results in 1.7B reads and 833M writes. Not saving them on the other hand, will result in a total read and write count of 2.6B and 833M, respectively. In this case therefore, saving is beneficial.

B. Switching Order of Last Two Modes

As mentioned in Section III-D, switching the order of the last two modes impacts the data movement and hence the performance. To determine whether to switch or not, we use a data movement model that requires the total number of fibers at each level. The CSF format inherently contains the total number of fibers for the original (non switched order). However, this count is not available for the switched order. Creating a new CSF format to count the fiber information for the switched-mode will increase the overhead of decision-making.

Algorithm 10: Finding number of fibers if last two modes of the CSF representation of \mathcal{T} are swapped

```

input : Sparse tensor  $\mathcal{T}$ 
output: Number of fibers in 1-2-4-3 order
1 for  $th=0$  to number of thread - 1 do in parallel
2   for row = 0 to  $n_3-1$  do
3     | observed[th][row]  $\leftarrow 0$ 
4     | num_fibers[th]  $\leftarrow 0$ 
5 for  $i \in \mathcal{T}(*,*,*,*)$  do in parallel
6   | th  $\leftarrow$  thread id
7   | for  $j \in \mathcal{T}(i,*,*,*)$  do
8     | for  $k \in \mathcal{T}(i,j,*,*)$  do
9       | for  $l \in \mathcal{T}(i,j,k,*)$  do
10      | | if observed[th][l]! = (i, j) then
11      | | | observed[th][l]  $\leftarrow$  (i, j)
12      | | | Increment num_fibers[th] by 1
13 number_fibers  $\leftarrow 0$ 
14 for  $th=0$  to number of thread - 1 do
15 | number_fibers  $\leftarrow$  number_fibers + num_fibers[th]

```

Algorithm 10 efficiently computes the fiber information for the switched order. Note that, since $d-2$ modes are the same for both original and switched order, the number of fibers for them is the same. Hence, we only need to compute the number of non-zeros after the first contraction of MTTKRP in the switched order. In Algorithm 10, we use a buffer of size $num_threads * n_3$, where n_3 is the length of the third dimension of the tensor. Each thread initializes its portion of the buffer to 0 (Line 4). Line 5 distributes the root mode of the tensor across multiple threads. In Line 10, each thread checks whether it has previously seen the $\langle i, j, l \rangle$ pair. If an pair was seen for the first time, we increment the fiber count (Line 12). Line 15 aggregates the fibre count across multiple threads.

C. Data Movement Model

Let x_i be the total number of read access to the i^{th} factorization matrix of size $N_i * R$. Each such access reads R elements (ie. one row) of the i^{th} factorization matrix. If the data footprint of the matrix is less than or equal to the cache size, each element will be loaded only once to the cache (cold miss) and reused thereafter. Otherwise, each x_i access will read R elements from the memory without reuse. Hence the data movement associated with i^{th} factorization matrix ($DM_factor_i(x_i)$) can be computed as follows:

$$DM_factor_i(x_i) = \begin{cases} x_i * R & N_i * R > cachesize \\ \min(N_i * R, x_i * R) & otherwise \end{cases}$$

Let m_i be the number of fibers at level i . Assuming that there is no memoization, for all modes, the read cost can be expressed as:

$$DM_no_mem_read = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} (2 * m_i + DM_factor_i(m_i))$$

If memoization is enabled, we can avoid the reads required to compute the intermediate tensor, but we must read the

partial results. Let k be the first mode that has been memoized where $i \leq k$. The corresponding read cost can be expressed as:

$$DM_mem_k_read = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (2 * m_i + DM_factor_i(m_i) + m_i * R)$$

The write cost corresponding to mode i can be expressed as:

$$DM_write = DM_factor_i(x_i)$$

VI. RELATED WORK

Smith et al. [2] proposed SPLATT which can compute CPD for tensor with using only a single CSF representation. This has also been extended to accelerate distributed tucker decomposition in [16]. Baskaran et al. [17] propose a split-reorder of the mode-contraction loop in the Tucker decomposition algorithm, such that partially contracted tensors can be re-used in an optimal manner. The tradeoff between storing partially contracted sparse tensors vs recomputing them, seems to have originated in Kolda et al [18], again in the context of Tucker decomposition. Kaya et al [3] proposed a novel sparse tensor representation for the CP decomposition algorithm. The Balanced Dimension Tree recursively partitions the set of modes into two halves. Each leaf hence contains a single mode. Each of the n mode contractions therefore involves a walk from the corresponding leaf to all internal nodes, via the root. Since several internal nodes are common among consecutive walks, the partially decomposed tensors corresponding to these nodes can be stored in memory. The only restriction for reuse is that the factor matrices are updated in sequential order. The partially decomposed tensors that used these factor matrices hence have to be recomputed. While this work focuses on the distributed memory setting, it also exploits intra-node shared memory parallelism. The corresponding *HyperTensor* library implementation has not yet been released to open-source, making an empirical comparison impossible for this work.

Li et al. [4] proposed a similar approach to choose different memoizations based on a model. They introduce a new storage format $vCSF$ to store the sparse tensor. For the n MTTKRP operations in total, they propose to store and reuse $\theta(\sqrt{N})$ partially contracted tensors. Coupled with mode reordering, this scheme essentially uses a CSF forest with the lower half of each CSF tree stored in memory for reuse. The implementation is named *AdaTM*, and has been used as one of the baselines for performance comparison.

More recently, Helal et al. [5] proposed a new compressed format called ALTO for storing tensors. This approach offers better load balancing and locality while performing a single MTTKRP. Furthermore, it also avoids the need to change the tensor representation for performing the different MTTKRPs in a CPD iteration. The storage structure uses a novel indexing representation for the nonzero elements of a sparse tensor that is formed by permuting a compacted binary representation of concatenated multi-dimensional index coordinates of tensor

elements. The work currently computes all mode contractions from scratch, and hence has a significantly higher FLOP count. We also compare performance with ALTO in Section VII.

Li et al. have also proposed mode reordering algorithms *BFS – MCS* and *Lexi – Order* [6]. The *Lexi – Order* seems to consistently outperform the hypergraph partitioning-based *BFS – MCS*. As per *Lexi – Order*, the lower-stride modes of the given ordering are sorted in increasing order of co-ordinates. It can easily be applied to COO, HiCOO or CSF representations in memory, and seems to improve speedup significantly in each case. For the CSF-based implementation, this seems to be complimentary to our contributions viz model-based storage of intermediate results.

Shivakumar et al. [19] propose a new compressed sparse symmetric *CSS* structure specifically for sparse symmetric tucker decomposition. This format exploits the constraint of a single factor matrix, and a core tensor with all dimensions of equal length. While this pushes the pareto front of runtime vs memory, this method currently is restricted to symmetric decomposition only.

The TACO compiler has integrated several optimizations for tensor decomposition and hence simplified the search across the entire optimization space, including the choice of mode orderings [15] [20] [21]. We consider the latest scheduling TACO implementation as one of our baselines for performance comparison.

VII. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

The experimental evaluation was performed on an 18 core Intel i9-10980XE (Cascade Lake) processor, using GCC v9.3.0. Operating system of the machine is Ubuntu 20.04.2 LTS and it has 128 GB (8x16 GB) memory installed. For benchmarking, we use the same set of tensors that have been used in previous studies on sparse tensor factorization, from the FROSTT [22] and HaTen2 [23] datasets. The properties of tensors used in the experiments are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I: List of tensors used in the experiments

Tensor	Dimensions	NNZ
chicago-crime-comm	6Kx24x77x32	5M
chicago-crime-geo	6Kx24x380x395x32	6M
delicious-3d	533Kx17Mx2M	140M
delicious-4d	533Kx17Mx2Mx1K	140M
enron	6Kx6Kx244Kx1K	54M
flickr-3d	320Kx28Mx2M	113M
flickr-4d	320Kx28Mx2Mx731	113M
freebase_music	23Mx23Mx166	100M
freebase_sampled	38Mx38Mx533	100M
lbnl-network	2Kx4Kx2Kx4Kx868K	2M
nell-1	3Mx2Mx25M	144M
nell-2	12Kx9Kx29K	77M
nips	2Kx3Kx14Kx17	3M
uber	183x24x1Kx2K	3M
vast-2015-mc1-3d	165Kx11Kx2	26M
vast-2015-mc1-5d	165Kx11Kx2x100x89	26M

B. Performance Comparison

We have compared our STeF algorithm against multiple state-of-the-art algorithms – Adatm [4], ALTO [5], Splatt 2.0.0 [14] and TACO [15]. Splatt has multiple versions for a single CPD iteration where it can use one, two, or as many as the number of dimensions of the tensors CSF representations; we called these variants Splatt-1, Splatt-2, and Splatt-A. Figure 4 compares relative speedup of other approaches compared to our STeF algorithm. STeF achieves 463%, 74%, 165%, 115%, 98% and 16% geomean speed-up over Adatm, ALTO, splatt-1, splatt-2, splatt-A and TACO respectively. Our performance is lower than Adatm, Splatt-2, Splatt-A and TACO in nell-2 tensor. This can be attributed to using a slow saxpy kernel for the leaf mode rather than using efficient dot product kernel. Adatm edges slightly over STeF in nell-1 because the length of modes in nell-1 is similar; hence for this case, there is no significant algorithmic difference between our approach and ADATM. TACO is performing better in delicious-3d and nell-1, where the length of the modes are too different and benefits of the saving the intermediate results are not as effective. Overall, TACO is better than Splatt-A even though they are very similar methods. Main reason for that is TACO is auto-tuning across various chunk sizes and picks the best for the experiments; thus, paying some preprocessing overhead for faster run time. Also, ALTO is performing better than STeF on vast-2015-mc1-5d tensor. For all the remaining cases, STeF performs better than the state-of-the-art solutions and achieves over 16% speedup on average with respect to best among all the state-of-the-art approaches.

C. Preprocessing Overhead

Figure 5 shows the preprocessing overhead associated with finding the number of fibers in different modes and determining whether we should use switch order or not (Algorithm 10). Preprocessing overhead average was 12% of a set of MTTKRP operations (or a single CPD iteration), and the maximum slowdown is below 100%. Typically CPD algorithms require many iterations to converge; Since preprocessing overhead is less than a single CPD iteration, preprocessing for finding the fiber counts to determine the order of the last two modes is negligible.

D. Additional Space Requirement

Table II shows the additional space requirement to use memoization technique of STeF. Overall, additional space requirement for the partial MTTKRP results is on average 33% of the space requirement for the CSF structure and the factorization matrices and this ratio is at most 2. This low space requirement for the STeF is partly thanks to selective memoization of the partial MTTKRP results using the model. The model tends to not memoize if memoizing a partial result is increasing the total data movement volume. This also helps avoiding big penalties for storing partial MTTKRPs. For example, in chicago-crime-comm the ratio of partial MTTKRP compared CSF and factorization matrices would have been 5.43 if all the partial MTTKRP have been saved.

Fig. 4: Results for number of factors = 32 for 18 core Cascade Lake Processor (higher the better).

Fig. 5: Preprocessing overhead for calculating whether to switch orders or not in 18 core Cascade Lake processor. Each bar represents preprocessing overhead to one set of MTTKRP operations.

Fig. 6: Speedup of the full design space and model space w.r.t. the model chosen configuration on an 18 core Intel Cascade Lake processor (lower the better).

E. Model Validation

The possible space of optimizations includes (i) whether we should save the intermediate results or not and (ii) the permutation choice. For a d dimensional tensor, $d - 2$ partial MTTKRP results can be saved. Therefore, the total number of choices is $2 \times 2^{d-2}$. For example, the total number of choices are 8, 16, and 32 configurations for 3D, 4D, and 5D tensors, respectively. The total number of permutation choices for a d dimensional tensor is $d!$. Therefore, the full design space is $d! \times 2^{d-2}$; thus, the full design space has 12, 96, and

960 configurations for 3D, 4D, and 5D tensors, respectively. However, among all possible permutations, our model only considers two – the original order and the order in which the last two modes are switches. Thus our model space contains $2 \times 2^{d-2}$ configurations. Figure 6 compares the performance of our model predicted configuration against the best possible choice. The performance of the model selected configuration is almost always identical to the best performing configuration in the model space, and the loss of performance is within 10%. Compared to the full design space average slow down is 12%.

Fig. 7: Ablation study for different optimizations presented in this paper on an 18 core Intel Cascade Lake processor. Performance is normalized with respect to the model-chosen configuration. 100% means same performance as the model-chosen configuration and below 100% means slower.

TABLE II: Space requirement for storing the partial MTTKRP results.

Tensor	Size of stored partial MTTKRP (GB)	Size of Tensor and Factorization Matrices (GB)	Ratio
chicago-crime-comm	0.01	0.08	0.13
chicago-crime-geo	0.04	0.15	0.29
delicious-3d	8.92	7.49	1.19
delicious-4d	14.84	7.85	1.89
enron	0.22	0.88	0.25
flickr-3d	3.18	9.06	0.35
flickr-4d	6.30	9.25	0.68
freebase_music	0.00	13.51	0.00
freebase_sampled	0.00	21.94	0.00
libnl-network	0.01	0.24	0.05
nell-1	4.14	9.71	0.43
nell-2	0.08	1.16	0.07
nips	0.00	0.05	0.04
uber	0.00	0.06	0.02
vast-2015-mc1-3d	0.06	0.43	0.14
vast-2015-mc1-5d	0.00	0.64	0.00

F. Ablation Study

Figure 7 show the effectiveness of the optimization presented in this paper. We chose the model selected configuration as the baseline configuration.

1) *Work Distribution*: To compare the effectiveness of our work distribution scheme, we compare the performance of our model selection configuration with and without our load balancing. Turning off our work distribution, on average, 39% slow down on MTTKRP performance. There are two cases where our work distribution was slightly slower than the slice-based parallelism.

2) *Saving Partial MTTKRs*: To measure the impact of our model, which predicts whether to save the intermediate results or not, we compare our results against two extreme choices (i) save all intermediate results, and (ii) don't save any intermediate results. As shown in Figure 7, our model has a significant impact on 3 of the tensors, and on average, it speeds up MTTKRP by 7%.

3) *Switching Order*: Our model also predicts whether we should switch the order of the last two modes or nodes. In order to assess this impact, we compare our approach against an approach that chooses the opposite choice as that of our model. As shown in Figure 7 this choice is significant for many tensors, and the *average slowdown for the opposite choice configuration is 40%*.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we develop a data movement-aware MTTKRP algorithm targeted at applications like CPD. Our proposed solution achieves good load balancing and reduced data movement using a single CSF representation of the tensor. We explore the design space of possible configurations for MTTKRP and develop an efficient model to select a good configuration. Our experimental section demonstrates the superiority of our approach compared to the state-of-the-art methods.

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